

PHYSIOTRENDS

ROLE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY IN OSTEONECROSIS OF HIP AFTER COVID – 19

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Osteonecrosis of hip or Avascular necrosis (AVN) of hip, is the vascular disruption of the hip joint lead to the death of the femoral head. AVN is more common in males than in females. Most Commonly clinically presents as the insidious onset of pain around the hip and restricted range of motion of hip Joint that lead to patients have a problem in weight bearing and during walking. Patients cannot walk properly.

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Most people infected with the virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment.¹ D-dimer elevation is often observed in patients with acute COVID-19 due acute lung injury itself or due thromboembolic complications that occur frequently in COVID-19.² Thromboembolism can damaged nearby blood vessels and reduce blood flow to bones lead to AVN can developed. Those who are suffering from Mild to Moderate COVID-19 they take more amount of corticosteroids during the acute phase of infection. Use of high-dose corticosteroids, such as prednisone can increase lipid levels in the blood, reducing blood flow.³ Due to Increase Lipid Levels and more Thromboembolism the cases of AVN Hip is increasing day by day.

Physiotherapy Can be used for relief of symptoms of Pain and Restricted ROM of hip joint. It can be help to prevent of disease progression and Improvement of functional activity and ADL. Physical therapy treatment focuses on exercises to maintain joint mobility and strengthen the muscles around the affected hip joint. Exercises will focus on the muscles of the hip and thigh but will also include exercises for the core area as they play a large supporting role. To improve functionality, it is important to implement endurance training and coordination training in a more advanced stage of the therapy.⁴

References :

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